

Impacts of Reproductive Health on Women's Life

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Introduction:

Healthy women directly or indirectly contribute to many important tasks for the family and society. Yet female health is neglected. Reproductive health problems arise in both women and men. The types of these problems, their causes, and their consequences are different, as the social roles and attitudes of women and men in society are different. Men also suffer from reproductive health problems, especially sexually transmitted diseases, although women suffer from several factors. Indian women live in a tight social class. In this category, the woman learns to control her freedom, to suppress her own needs. Learns to be submissive or submissive which affects her social, economic, family, occupational as well as health status and her condition becomes more difficult, especially during different stages of female reproductive health.

Female Reproductive Health:

According to the World Health Organization, 'health is the state of being physically, mentally and socially well; It's not just the lack of disease. "Thus being free from disease is not only health but also physical, mental, and social well-being. The World Health Organization states that "reproductive health addresses reproductive processes, functions, and mechanisms at all stages of life." Reproductive health means people can lead responsible, satisfying,

and safe sex lives. They have the power to reproduce and the freedom to decide when and how many children to give birth to. Men and women have the right to adopt and receive safe, effective, affordable, and preferred contraceptive methods. They have the right to access appropriate healthcare services. It makes women safer during pregnancy and childbirth as well as gives couples the best chance of having a healthy baby.

Stages of female reproductive health

Adolescence

(Onset of menstruation)

Puberty

(Menopause)

Youth

(Pregnancy)

The three main stages of the female reproductive period

- 1) The stage of the onset of menstruation
- 2) The stage of conception to childbirth
- 3) The stage of menopause

1. Menstrual onset phase:

Compared to Western countries in the world, India has more problems related to women's health. It is a fact that adolescents in India are less skilled in making decisions about their own lives and gaining consensus on a subject through negotiations, as evidenced by early marriage and early conception. The onset of menstruation is significant in physical transformation. When girls reach the age of 11-12 years, they start undergoing two types of changes, physical and mental. At this early age, they have a variety of emotions that they do not understand, as well as many questions. But they can't ask anyone anything because of embarrassment. Also, in our family or our schools, we don't talk about it openly. Besides, even if women have menstruation, they do not know where it comes from. What to do if pain occurs? What to take care of then? Some girls are

discriminated against in their childhood. Sometimes sex choices, sexual abuse, early marriage and the associated physical and mental health risks, abortions due to unexpected pregnancies, sexually transmitted diseases, and AIDS can occur.

Problems during menstruation

- Many women have a slight change in temperament during their menstruation, some get irritable, some start crying, and some don't like to work or talk to someone. This usually happens to many women.
- During the menstrual cycle, certain households observe certain beliefs. For example, do not touch the pot of water, do not fill the water from the well or river, do not go near the stove, or make pickles at that time so that the girls are embarrassed.
- Menstruation is not measurable, but women who menstruate for more than seven days, menstruate twice a month, have large blood clots, or have to change pads frequently are called more menstrual. Diseases of the uterus or

ovaries may also be responsible for more menstruation.

- Many women have white water two to three days before menstruation, and if it is accompanied by itching or odor, there is a possibility of uterine infection.
- Due to the changes in the body's hormones, sometimes a woman experiences swelling, heaviness in the chest, constipation, insomnia, irritability, etc. a few days before menstruation.
- During menstruation, the uterine muscles contract to stretch the wall as well as the area. The veins (nerves) of these muscles of the uterus are thickened in the thighs and legs. This causes pain in the waist, gums, and legs when the uterine muscles contract.

2. The stage of conception and childbirth

- Unplanned pregnancies, unsafe pregnancies, unsafe abortions, pregnancy complications, etc. are major health issues during women's reproductive years.
- Usually, the family is concerned about women's health when the baby is about to be born but there is no improvement with the period before or after.
- The fertility of women is also controlled in many ways. In many societies, women do not have the freedom to decide on their desire to have a child as well as how many children they want.
- The difference in the number of women and men shows that women are tested during pregnancy and are forced to have abortions against their will.
- Women often do not even have an understanding of the state of the disease. Excessive menstruation has adverse effects on her health. Which annoys him physically as well as mentally and gradually this suffering becomes a part of his life.
- Most women are unaware of the physical changes caused by hormones. Precautions to be taken during pregnancy are often not adopted by them, thus increasing the chances of miscarriage.
- The death of a pregnant mother is not an accidental event, apart from the medical reasons responsible for the death of the pregnant mother, many factors such as poverty, the lower status of women, gender discrimination, inadequate information, and knowledge about danger signs are also responsible.
- Women often lose control of their bodies as they underestimate their importance and lack of determination to use contraceptives leads to unwanted pregnancies.
- The lack of safe abortion facilities leads to unsafe abortions for women.

- Women are victims of physical violence during pregnancy and do not receive help or cooperation from their families during such crises.
- Social gender discrimination at the health service level also affects women's health. The low gender sensitivity, lack of foresight, lack of rights as well as empowerment approach of social gender equality of workers providing health services also harm women's health.

Mental changes a woman experiences after pregnancy

- Many women feel a sudden change in their mood 2-3 days after delivery. She seems to cry a little, she gets angry, she doesn't like anything. I don't understand why this happens etc. It lasts for about 10-12 days and then decreases.
- During this time the family needs to give the woman patience and warmth. Giving a little empathy and love benefits the mother a lot.
- The scientific reason for this is not yet known. Perhaps there is a belief that this is due to a change in hormones.
- At this stage, the woman becomes depressed so she is constantly very sad and dejected. She can't take care of her child in the same way. She stays silent all day, doesn't do any work, and everything happens that she can't sleep at night. Sometimes she even thinks of dying.
- If depression lasts for a long time then the atmosphere in the house is very stressful and anxious. It also has a detrimental effect on a child's upbringing.

3. The stage of menopause

In women, menstruation becomes irregular, decreases, and gradually stops at a certain age. The next woman's life is called menopause. The changes that take place during this period can be divided into four parts.

1. Early menopause and problems arising from it.
 2. Changes in the secretion of various endocrine hormones and the problems caused by them.
 3. Changes in the entire skeletal structure of the body, especially in the bones of the spine and hips, and the difficulties that come in the life of women due to it.
- A woman's ovaries secrete two types of hormones: estrogen and progesterone. Both of these hormones cause physical changes in a woman, menstruation, pregnancy, and childbirth as well as her physical and mental strength due to both these hormones. From the age of 10 to 12 years, both endometrioses start from the ovaries and when a woman reaches the age of 45 to 50 years, these endocrine secretions stop and the woman stops menstruating.
 - Most women usually start menopause between the ages of 45 and 50. But in some cases, a

woman goes through menopause at the age of 40, or even after 55 years.

- Short-term problems such as extreme heat, hot flashes, headaches, and backaches, and mental problems such as anxiety, mood swings, irritability, etc. occur during menopause. Most of these problems last for 1 to 2 years.
- During menopause, women feel that they can no longer be young and look older, so they often feel that this condition will affect their sexual desire.
- Irregular menstruation during menopause, difficulty urinating, vaginal contractions, or difficulty having sex can occur for a few years.
- Prolonged changes after menopause include problems such as weakening of the bones.
- Many women experience memory loss after the onset of menopause. New events are forgotten but old ones are remembered. E.g. Where are the glasses or keys, no one remembers to go there, etc.

The life cycle of women, (1) the onset of menstruation, (2) conception, childbirth, and (3) endocrine changes in the stage of menopause cause dangerous situations as part of physical, mental, and sensory changes.

Effects of Reproductive Health on Female Life:

Confusions such as the onset of menstruation in adolescents arouse curiosity. Adolescents in this state need the necessary information and mental warmth about the changes that take place in them. They lack information on what to do, where to go, as well as reproductive health information. Similarly, many women experience a lot of stress during the sensitive stages of pregnancy and menopause.

Menstrual status:

- Two out of 10 adolescents have become pregnant at the age of 15-16 or have given birth to one child.
- 9 out of 10 teenagers get married before the age of 18.
- 9 out of 10 adolescents aged 15-16 have anemia in their blood.
- Every other teenager between the ages of 15-16 is underweight.
(Source: National Family Health Survey-3 Gujarat, 2005-2006)
- The marriage rate in India below 18 years is 4.5%
- The marriage rate under 18 years in Gujarat is 2.5% in Gujarat
- Maternal Pregnancy Rate in India at the age of 15-16% 7.5%
- The maternal conception rate in Gujarat at the age of 15-16 years is 2.5%
(Source: National Family Health Survey-4, 2015-16)

- In adolescence, the nutritional needs of pregnancy are often not met.
- Inadequate facilities for maintaining personal hygiene increase the chances of infection.
- Lack of control over one's body leads to low self-esteem and leads to disregard.
- Women who marry at a young age and have a long reproductive period give birth to more children. Frequent childbirth makes a woman physically weak. Combining poverty with frequent pregnancies has a dangerous effect on a woman's physical and mental health.

Pregnancy status:

- According to the World Health Organization (WHO), the maternal mortality rate in India is 130 per 1 lakh live births in 2014-16.
- According to the World Health Organization (WHO), the maternal mortality rate in Gujarat is 91 per 1 lakh live births in 2014-16.
- According to the World Health Organization, the rate of postpartum depression in the world is 0.2 to 4.5% per 1,000 live births.
- Stress also affects a woman's physical health. This is accepted in modern medical science.
- During pregnancy and after childbirth, a woman is also plagued with some mental health issues such as mood disorders, postpartum disorders, and baby blues problems. If a woman in this condition does not receive proper mental health treatment, she will suffer from serious mental health diseases for the rest of her life and may even commit suicide.
- In a couple who does not have children, scientifically, about 30% of the reasons may be due to the man's physical discomfort, 40% of the reasons may be due to the woman's physical discomfort and the remaining 30% may be due to some defect or some other reason. But in our society, women are held responsible for not having children. New fertility techniques such as test-tube babies (in vitro fertilization) are rapidly evolving due to the desire to have a child born from one's own body. Techniques such as amniocentesis and ultrasonography have led to an increase in the number of fetuses being killed knowing the sex of the fetus.

Menopause

- According to N F H S-4, 2015-16, the rate of uterine surgery for women aged 15-49 in India is 3%.
- N F H S- 4, 2015-16 As per Gujarat, the rate of uterine surgery for women aged 15-49 is 6.6%.
- There are two reasons for menopause (1) natural and (2) artificial
- Naturally, menstruation gradually decreases and stops after 20 to 5 years. When menstruation

stops for 1 year or more, a woman is naturally called menopause.

- When the uterine cavity and both ovaries are removed, the woman stops menstruating from that time onwards, which is called artificial menopause.
- Decreased ovarian hormone (estrogen) in menopause reduces a woman's strength, she feels tired, and she has difficulties in household and daily work, which affects her family as well as her professional life.
- At this stage, women are in dire need of the support and cooperation of their families, but when they are not satisfied, they sometimes fall into depression.
- Due to incapacity-fatigue, a woman does not have the same concentration in her work as before, so her enthusiasm for work decreases. Along with this, she also has family as well as children issues, which results in irritability, anger, and other behavioral problems.

Women's problems are widespread and acute. In which various stages of reproductive health affect her entire life. In India, efforts are being made to address women's reproductive health issues through various government schemes and the efforts of voluntary organizations. These schemes are implemented by government officials or activists. But it has many flaws. Since the number is high, the employees consider the beneficiaries only as a target. So that women are deprived of the rightful beneficiaries of the scheme. So that women cannot achieve a true understanding of reproductive health.

Effective actions:

- **Steps to be taken by the school to ensure that adolescents do not panic during the first menstrual period as they are unaware of the menstrual process and get the necessary information.**

School teachers should receive training on reproductive health, for which the school principal should arrange (1) a gynecologist, (2) a specialist worker of a voluntary organization working in a health-related field, and (3) any suitable specialist from the government health department. In which the district-level D.E.O. office must provide the funding or approval for such training programs.

The school should show a documentary to provide information on reproductive health to students. Which can be available from voluntary organizations working in the field of female reproductive health.

- **Steps to be taken by voluntary organizations working for reproductive health**

Information on the physical and mental changes during different stages of women's reproductive health in rural and urban areas and the role of

family members at that time should be disseminated through various media such as handing out small information leaflets on various stages of reproductive health to local PHC, CHC or Anganwadi Centers. Establish regular distribution arrangements. Organizing meetings with women from different areas. Voluntary organizations should open a cell to the best of their ability to make reproductive health information easily accessible to people and to ease their problems. Where through proper advice and guidance women's reproductive health can bring relief to physical and mental problems. Every organization should try to inform the counselors working in the multi-purpose women's welfare centers run at the district level through training on reproductive health issues. So that the women who come there for guidance can get awareness about their reproductive health as well as inform their family members and male members of their family about women's reproductive health issues and change their attitudes.

- **Steps to be taken by government departments working on women's health**

Workers of different departments benefiting from the scheme such as Anganwadi Workers, Female Health Workers, and Asha Workers should all be given a comprehensive understanding of reproductive health conditions as well as their effects on women's physical and mental health through training so that they can inform women's families about these conditions. Taking special care can explain them.

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